

A Randomized, Double-Blind Clinical Assessment of the Effect of Low-Dose Nicotinic Acid on Hyperphosphatemia in Patients with ESRD.

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Abstract:

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the effect of low-dose nicotinic acid on hyperphosphatemia in patients with ESRD.

Methods: In this randomized, double-blind clinical trial, 100 dialysis patients referred to the Department of Nephrology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for the period of six months were evaluated.

Results: The difference in mean age between niacin and placebo groups was not significant. At the end of the first month, the difference between two groups in calcium level was significant. At the end of the second month, the difference between the two groups in terms of phosphorus and calcium levels was significant. At the end of the third month, mean phosphorus level was significantly different between the two groups.

Conclusion: We concluded that niacin (100 mg/day) decreased phosphorus serum level and increased HDL serum level in patients on dialysis.

Keywords: End Stage Renal Disease, High-Density Lipoprotein, Hyperphosphatemia, Nicotinic Acid.

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Introduction

Hyperphosphatemia is a frequent complication of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) and principally affects hemodialysis (HD) patients. Elevated serum phosphorus contributes to the development of secondary hyperparathyroidism, chronic kidney disease-mineral bone disorder (CKD-MBD), metastatic calcifications, and calcific uremic arteriopathy. There is a significant association between hyperphosphatemia and increased morbidity and mortality in ESRD patients including cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, also it is associated with the hospitalization of HD patients. [1] Although there are multiple lines of treatment of hyperphosphatemia in ESRD patients undergoing HD, they are still inadequate. Calcium-containing phosphate binders sometimes cause adverse effects such as hypercalcemia and coronary calcification, the non-calcium-containing phosphate binders, such as sevelamer and lanthanum are expensive. Moreover, aluminum-containing agents are efficient, but no longer used because of their toxicity. Several trials have shown that nicotinamide (NAM) and niacin can reduce serum phosphate levels markedly in patients undergoing HD. [2] Niacin was initially reported to lower plasma cholesterol. [3] The main clinical use of

niacin has been to raise high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol and reduce triglyceride levels with potentially favorable cardiovascular effects. Recently, nicotinic acid and related compounds such as nicotinamide (NAM) have also shown to decrease phosphorus absorption in the gastrointestinal tracts of animals through a unique mechanism other than the traditional phosphate binders. [4]

In prior research, nicotinic acid has been demonstrated to be safe, cheap, and effective in normalizing serum phosphorus and Ca-P product in patients with ESRD. [5] Flushing, a common side effect of nicotinic acid, can be overcome by premedication with aspirin. [6] Although most side effects are reversible, further studies are warranted to investigate the safety profile of this potential therapeutic option. [7] Despite these positive roles of niacin, physicians hesitate to prescribe niacin because of its various adverse effects such as hot flushing, liver function test abnormality and thrombocytopenia. Although some of these adverse effects are mild and easily controlled by symptomatic care, some effects such as hot flushing necessitate cessation of niacin

administration. [8,9] Therefore, it is necessary to judge whether the benefits of low-dose niacin administration outweighs its adverse effects. Edalat-Nejad et al. (2012) suggested that niacin may emerge as a safe and low-cost therapy in combination with other phosphate binders for phosphate control. [10]

The aim of the present study was to assess the effect of low-dose nicotinic acid on hyperphosphatemia in patients with ESRD.

Materials and Methods

In this randomized, double-blind clinical trial, 100 dialysis patients referred to the Department of Nephrology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for the period of six months were evaluated.

Inclusion criteria were age >18 years, ability to give informed consent, $PO_4 \geq 5.5$ mg/dl, dialysis duration for more than 3 months, adequate dialysis (Kt/V >1.2) during the study. Exclusion criteria were pregnancy, liver disease, active peptic ulcer disease, taking carbamazepine, history of niacin (or niacin as other drugs' component) sensitivity, and malignancy.

Written informed consent was obtained before randomization, as per the institution's protocol. The study was approved by Ethical Committee. The patients were randomly assigned to either niacinamide or placebo groups. Both participants and the study staff (site investigators and trial coordinating staff) were masked to the treatment. Niacin and placebo were packaged in identical tablets by pharmacy. The patients were prescribed

one tablet daily with their meal. Dosages were titrated from 25 mg/day over 12 weeks.

Phosphorus level was measured pretreatment and at the end of weeks 4, 8, and 12. When serum phosphorus levels did not reach the normal reference range ($P \leq 5.5$ mg/dl), the dose of nicotinic acid was increased to 50 mg/day at the end of the 1st month and to 100 mg/day at the end of the 3rd month. None of the participants was treated with sevelamer (renagel). Wash-out period was not permitted by the Ethics Committee, thus, all patients were administered 1500 mg calcium carbonate as phosphate binder during the study. When phosphorus levels exceeded 5.5 mg/dl or decreased to less than 3.5 mg/dl, the dose of phosphate binder was changed in order to continue niacin at the described dose. None of the participants used statins. The patients were followed for 3 months and during this period, serum levels of P, Ca, alanine aminotransferase (ALP), HDL cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), platelet, and parathyroid hormone (PTH) were measured monthly.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics that used mean and standard deviation are presented as continuous variables. The Chi-square and Fisher's exact test

were used to compare categorical variables. Mann-Whitney's U-test and paired t-test were used to compare continuous variables. For all the tests, ($P \leq 0.05$) was considered significant. Data were analyzed using SPSS 20 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

Results

Table 1: The mean and standard deviation of parameters at the end of first month in two groups (25 mg/day niacin)

Parameters	Niacin	Placebo	P
P (mg/dl)	6.6±0.74	6.5±1.4	0.424
Ca(mg/dl)	8.2±1.5	9.2±1.6	0.005
PTH (pg/ml)	318.2±212	282.8±234.6	0.486
Cholesterol(mg/dl)	143.7±44.6	156.4±32.2	0.088
TG (mg/dl)	132.8±38.8	128.2±28.2	0.785
LDL(mg/dl)	68.2±20.8	69.1±35.5	0.445
HDL(mg/dl)	45±14.6	45.1±12.6	0.932
AST (IU/L)	22.6±6.4	22.1±6.2	0.632
ALT (IU/L)	23.7±12.8	22±6.4	0.535
Bilirubin (mg/dl)	1.05±0.23	1±0.38	0.175
Platelet count, $\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$	21,224.0±50,765.2	23,935.0±61,009.2	0.69

The difference in mean age between niacin and placebo groups was not significant. At the end of the first month, the difference between two groups in calcium level was significant.

Table 2: The mean and standard deviation of parameters at the end of second month in two groups (50 mg/day niacin)

Parameters	Niacin	Placebo	P
P (mg/dl)	1.2±5.4	1.5±6.4	0.001
Ca(mg/dl)	1.4±8.2	1.1±8.1	0.020
PTH (pg/ml)	192.8±316.2	214.6±2275	0.445
Cholesterol(mg/dl)	38±143.7	35.5±154.6	0.224
TG (mg/dl)	44.6±136.4	32.8±132.2	0.445
LDL(mg/dl)	18.2±72.4	17.3±68.2	0.635
HDL(mg/dl)	9.1±42.8	10±43.7	0.785
AST (IU/L)	6.3±18.4	7.4±20.8	0.735
ALT (IU/L)	5.5±18.2	6.6±21.1	0.248
Bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.24±0.96	0.32±1	0.240
Platelet count, ×10 ³ /mm ³	59894.9±233080	54931.5±242860	0.471

At the end of the second month, the difference between the two groups in terms of phosphorus and calcium levels was significant.

Table 3: The mean and standard deviation of parameters at the end of third month in two groups (100 mg/day niacin)

Parameters	Niacin	Placebo	P
P (mg/dl)	1.2±4.6	0.94±7.1	0.0001
Ca(mg/dl)	0.5±8.2	1.2±8.4	0.325
PTH (pg/ml)	186.8±306.4	201.3±259.7	0.309
Cholesterol(mg/dl)	32.8±146.4	32.6±156.4	0.220
TG(mg/dl)	54.6±136.5	36.2±134.6	0.555
LDL(mg/dl)	22.4±68.2	21.5±72.6	0.634
HDL(mg/dl)	12.8±48.2	11.6±45.5	0.545
AST (IU/L)	6.4±20.5	6.6±22.8	0.151
ALT (IU/L)	6.4±22.08	5.7±24.6	0.242
Bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.18±0.92	0.36±0.94	0.576
Platelet count, ×10 ³ /mm ³	58785.7±236244	47376.7±243675	0.546

At the end of the third month, mean phosphorus level was significantly different between the two groups.

Discussion

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is growing worldwide and the incidence of end stage renal diseases (ESRD) is on the rise. [11] Previous studies have reported that hyperphosphatemia results in increased morbidity and mortality among patients with CKD. Serum phosphorus levels more than 6.5 mg/dl increase mortality rate about 27% compared to phosphorus levels <6.5 mg/dl. [12,13] Long-term inadequate phosphate control leads to secondary hyperparathyroidism, metabolic bone diseases, calcific uremic arteriolopathy, and cardiovascular calcification. Progressive increases in arterial calcification are associated with higher rates of mortality. [14] Management of hyperphosphatemia in patients with ESRD is not adequate. Calcium containing phosphate binders may sometimes result in adverse effects such as hypercalcemia. [15] Noncalcium phosphate binders, such as sevelamer and lanthanum, are expensive. [16] The modest increase in HDL values may be considered as another beneficial effect of this treatment. Its major side effects are

vasodilation and flushing, and prostaglandins seems to be the cause, thus can be attenuated by premedication with aspirin. [17]

The global incidence of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) is increasing exponentially. By 2030, the number of individuals on dialysis is projected to reach 5.4 million, with the most growth expected in Asia. [18] Hyperphosphatemia is a potential cause of adverse clinical outcomes in ESRD. In patients on maintenance hemodialysis (HD), the mortality risk increases up to 27% with serum phosphorus levels >6.5 mg/dL compared to serum phosphorus levels ranging from 2.4 to 6.5 mg/dL. [19] Similarly, dismal results have been observed for calcium-phosphorus (Ca-P) product of >45.9 mg²/dL². Chronically elevated calcium has a predilection for precipitation in myocardium, blood vessels, and heart valves. [20] Therefore, appropriate treatment of hyperphosphatemia in patients with ESRD is imperative to decrease the risk of cardiovascular morbidity as well as renal complications, such as renal failure and renal osteodystrophy. [21]

The difference in mean age between niacin and placebo groups was not significant. At the end of the first month, the difference between two groups

in calcium level was significant. At the end of the second month, the difference between the two groups in terms of phosphorus and calcium levels was significant. At the end of the third month, mean phosphorus level was significantly different between the two groups. In line with the results of this study, Vasantha et al., in an open-label study on 30 dialysis patients receiving a dose of NAM 750 mg/day, reported reductions in serum phosphorus level (2.3 mg/dl). [22] Rennick et al., in a meta-analysis reviewed seven studies that evaluated the effect of nicotinamide and nicotinic acid on phosphorus serum level in ESRD patients undergoing dialysis and indicated that in the three studies using nicotinic acid as the therapeutic intervention and four studies using nicotinamide, both nicotinic acid and nicotinamide significantly reduced serum phosphorus level. [23] In the present study, no significant changes in Ca and PTH were detected. Cheng et al., observed insignificant changes in serum calcium and PTH levels in the niacin group. [24] In agreement with Kang et al., statistically significant increases in HDL were observed in the present study. [25]

Results from larger and more significant trials emphasize that the safety profile of nicotinic acid is controversial. [26] A sub-group analysis on a randomized controlled Atherothrombosis Intervention in Metabolic Syndrome with low HDL/High Triglycerides: Impact on Global Health Outcomes (AIM-HIGH) trial suggested more side effects (flushing) and fewer benefits resulting from nicotinic acid therapy. [27] The study enrolled 3414 cases and used extended-release niacin. A study comparing sevelamer and oral nicotinamide in 100 patients on HD suggested more side effects (major risk of thrombocytopenia) and less clinical effectiveness of nicotinamide. [28] Use of low-dose niacin is affordable due to low adverse effects and the low cost. Recent studies, suggested that after reducing side effects, nicotinamide can be an expensive alternative. [29] Therefore, a low dose of niacin may be helpful not only for the control of dyslipidemia, but also for the early prevention of hyperphosphatemia in patients with CKD. Meanwhile, a comparison with baseline revealed increased ALP level after niacin supplementation in our study. Increased ALP level after niacin supplementation was also found in animal and human studies.³⁰ However, further studies are recommended to examine if it is an acceptable alternative to sevelamer in patients with economic constraints.

Conclusion

We concluded that niacin (100 mg/day) decreased serum phosphorus level and increased serum HDL level in patients on dialysis. The results of our study have confirmed that niacin is an effective

drug in reducing serum phosphorus levels in dialysis patients in combination with other phosphate binders. Niacin may be considered as a safe, low-cost therapy, with fewer side effects, and fewer tablets are required to achieve good compliance. The slight elevation in HDL values may be considered as an added beneficial effect.

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